

1 **Supporting Information for**

2 **Selective sweep probabilities in spatially expanding populations**

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12 1. Proof of Claim 1

13 *Proof of claim 1.* By definition of the per capita mutation rate, we have $\mu N(t_1)dt$ successful mutations in the infinitesimal
14 time interval $[t_1, t_1 + dt]$. We sum over the time interval $[0, t]$ and obtain $\lambda = \int_0^t \mu N(t) dt$. We assume that mutations occur
15 independently of each other (infinite alleles) such that the stochastic process is a non-homogeneous Poisson process which has a
16 Poisson distribution with mean λ . \square

17 2. Connection between per-capita and per-division mutation rate

18 In our macroscopic model, we assume a constant per-capita mutation rate $\tilde{\mu}$. Often, it is assumed that mutations are coupled
19 to division. Here, we show how a per-capita mutation rate connects to a per-division mutation rate. Suppose that after each
20 division one of the two daughter cells obtains a driver mutation with probability p_μ . (The probability that both daughter cells
21 obtain a driver mutation scales with p_μ^2 , which can be neglected for sufficiently small p_μ .) Suppose cells divide at rate b and die
22 at rate d . If division rates are constant over time and space, then the per-division mutation probability p_μ yields a constant
23 per-capita mutation rate $\tilde{\mu} = p_\mu b$. The death rate may still differ in time and space.

24 3. Exact solution for the conditional sweep probability

25 We compute the full exact expression for the conditional sweep probability $\Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y)$ in 3D (eqn. 9 in the main
26 text). From the main text, we have

$$27 \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) = e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau}. \quad [1]$$

28 where $N_{\text{wt}}(\tau)$ is the size of the remaining wildtype population given in eqn. 6 in the main text. The integral is divided into

$$29 \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau = \int_0^{\tau_1} \tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_1(\tau) d\tau + \int_{\tau_1}^\infty \tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_2(\tau) d\tau. \quad [2]$$

30 Here, $\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau)$ and $\Delta_1(\tau)$ are the population sizes of the wildtype and mutant in case of undisturbed radial growth such that

$$31 \begin{aligned} \tilde{N}_{\text{wt}} &= \frac{4}{3}\pi x_{\text{wt}}^3(\tau) \\ \Delta_1(\tau) &= \frac{4}{3}\pi x_{\text{m}}^3(\tau). \end{aligned} \quad [3]$$

32 Further, $\Delta_2(\tau)$ is the intersecting volume of two balls with radii x_{wt} and x_{m} at distance y . Following ref. (1), we have

$$33 \Delta_2(\tau) = \frac{\pi}{12y}(x_{\text{wt}} + x_{\text{m}} + y)^2(y^2 + 2yx_{\text{m}} - 3x_{\text{m}}^2 + 2yx_{\text{wt}} + 6x_{\text{wt}}x_{\text{m}} - 3x_{\text{wt}}^2). \quad [4]$$

34 We express x_{wt} and x_{m} in terms of the wildtype radius at the time the first mutant occurred x and the time τ from the
35 emergence of the first mutant,

$$36 \begin{aligned} x_{\text{wt}}(\tau) &= c_{\text{wt}}t = c_{\text{wt}}(\tau + x/c_{\text{wt}}) \\ x_{\text{m}}(\tau) &= c_{\text{m}}\tau. \end{aligned} \quad [5]$$

37 Now, we are ready to integrate over $N_{\text{wt}}(\tau)$. We obtain

$$38 \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau = \frac{\pi(15x^4(3c_{\text{m}}^2 - 3c_{\text{m}}c_{\text{wt}} + c_{\text{wt}}^2) - y^4(23c_{\text{m}}^2 + 31c_{\text{m}}c_{\text{wt}} + 23c_{\text{wt}}^2) - 210c_{\text{m}}^2x^2y^2)}{45(c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}})^3}. \quad [6]$$

39 Inserting this into eqn. 1 gives us the conditional sweep probability. The exact solution reduces to the solution in the main
40 text with $y = 0$, for which

$$41 \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau = \frac{1}{\mu} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^4 \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3(c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}})^3}{\pi\mu(c_{\text{wt}}^2 - 3c_{\text{wt}}c_{\text{m}} + 3c_{\text{m}}^2)}}. \quad [7]$$

42 4. The sweep probability is independent of the mutation rate

43 We show that the unconditional selective sweep probability $\Pr(\text{sweep})$ (eqn. 11 in the main text) is independent of the mutation
44 rate. We start by defining homogeneous functions and stating a lemma for homogeneous functions. We then show how this
45 lemma proves independence of the unconditional sweep probability and eventually prove the lemma. Here, we focus on the
46 three-dimensional case whereas the independence for the two- and one-dimensional case is shown later.

47 **A. Homogeneous functions.**

48 **Definition 1.** A function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called homogeneous of degree k if

$$49 \quad f(sx_1, sx_2, \dots, sx_n) = s^k f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \quad [8]$$

50 for every x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and $s \neq 0$.

51 Noteworthy, polynomials in which all terms have the same polynomial degree k are homogeneous functions with degree k .
 52 For example, $5x^2y^2 + \pi x^4$ is homogeneous in x and y with degree 4.

53 **Lemma 1.** Let $\nu > 0$. Let $H(x, y)$, $P(x, y)$ and $Q(x, y)$ be homogeneous functions in x and y with degrees $h, p, q > 0$ respectively
 54 and $Q(x, y) \neq 0$ for all $x > 0$ and $y > 0$. Then, the integral

$$55 \quad I = \int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\nu H(x,y)} \frac{P(x,y)}{Q(x,y)} dy dx \quad [9]$$

56 is proportional to $\nu^{\frac{q-p-2}{h}}$.

57 **B. The sweep probability is independent of the mutation rate.** To apply the lemma on the unconditional sweep probability, we
 58 set $\nu = \mu$ and

$$59 \quad \begin{aligned} H(x, y) &= \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau + \frac{3c_{\text{wt}}}{\pi} x^4 \\ P(x, y) &= 3y^2 \times 4x^3 \\ Q(x, y) &= \frac{3c_{\text{wt}}}{\pi} x^3. \end{aligned} \quad [10]$$

60 It is straightforward that $P(x, y)$ and $Q(x, y)$ are homogeneous in x and y with degrees $p = 5$ and $q = 3$. Looking at eqn. 6, it
 61 is also apparent that $H(x, y)$ is homogeneous with degree 4. Using those expressions and applying lemma 1, we have

$$62 \quad \text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) = \mu \times I \propto \mu \times \mu^{\frac{3-5-2}{4}} = \mu^0, \quad [11]$$

63 which proves the independence of the mutation rate.

64 We found that the approximate solution using $f_Y(y|X=x) = \delta(y)$ is also independent of the mutation rate indicating a more
 65 general result. Looking at the derivation above, this becomes clear. Consider fixed equations for $\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}|X=x, Y=y)$ and
 66 $f_X(x)$. For any density function $f_Y(y|X=x)$ that is homogeneous in x and y with degree -1, we can define functions $P(x, y)$
 67 and $Q(x, y)$ such that their difference in degrees is $p - q = -2$. After the application of lemma 1, it follows independence.

68 **C. Proof of Lemma 1.**

69 *Proof of lemma 1.* We show the relation by making the substitutions

$$70 \quad \hat{x} = \nu^{1/h} x \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{y} = \nu^{1/h} y$$

71 such that

$$72 \quad \begin{aligned} H(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) &= \nu H(x, y) \\ P(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) &= \nu^{p/h} P(x, y) \\ Q(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) &= \nu^{q/h} Q(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

73 and

$$74 \quad dx = \nu^{-1/h} d\hat{x} \quad \text{and} \quad dy = \nu^{-1/h} d\hat{y}.$$

75 Inserting the substitutions in eqn. 9, we obtain

$$76 \quad \begin{aligned} I &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\nu H(x,y)} \frac{P(x,y)}{Q(x,y)} dy dx \\ &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^{\hat{x}} e^{-H(\hat{x},\hat{y})} \frac{\nu^{-p/h} P(\hat{x},\hat{y})}{\nu^{-q/h} Q(\hat{x},\hat{y})} \nu^{-1/h} \nu^{-1/h} d\hat{y} d\hat{x} \\ &= \nu^{-2/h} \nu^{(q-p)/h} \int_0^\infty \int_0^{\hat{x}} e^{-H(\hat{x},\hat{y})} \frac{P(\hat{x},\hat{y})}{Q(\hat{x},\hat{y})} d\hat{y} d\hat{x} \end{aligned}$$

77 The remaining integral is no longer dependent on parameter ν and shows the desired scaling with $\nu^{\frac{q-p-2}{h}}$. \square

78 5. Sweep probability in one dimension

79 We consider a population that is expanding in one dimension in two directions with constant speed. If x_{wt} describes the
80 length from the origin of the population to the leading edge, then the population size is $N_{\text{wt}} = 2x_{\text{wt}}(t) = 2c_{\text{wt}}t$. We follow the
81 derivations described in the main text.

82 **A. Arrival time and location of the first mutant.** We start by computing the probability density for the time at which the first
83 mutant arises. Using claim 1, we compute the probability that no mutant occurs until time t ,

$$84 P_0 = e^{-\mu \int_0^t 2c_{\text{wt}}t' dt'} = e^{-\mu c_{\text{wt}}t^2} = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa_{1\text{D}}}\right)^2} \quad \text{with} \quad \kappa_{1\text{D}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\mu c_{\text{wt}}}}. \quad [12]$$

85 The probability density function for the timing of the first surviving mutant is then

$$86 f_T(t) = \frac{d(1 - P_0)}{dt} = \frac{2t}{\kappa_{1\text{D}}^2} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa_{1\text{D}}}\right)^2}. \quad [13]$$

87 With a change of variables $t = \frac{x}{c_{\text{wt}}}$, we obtain the probability density for the population radius X at the time the first surviving
88 mutant arises, which is

$$89 f_X(x) = \frac{2x}{\theta_{1\text{D}}^2} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta_{1\text{D}}}\right)^2} \quad \text{with} \quad \theta_{1\text{D}} = \sqrt{\frac{c_{\text{wt}}}{\mu}}. \quad [14]$$

90 Since all distances y from the wildtype origin have the same amount of proliferating cells, the probability density for the location
91 of the first surviving mutant Y conditional on $X = x$ is given by a homogeneous probability density. After consideration of
92 boundary conditions and normalization, we have

$$93 f_Y(y|X = x) = \frac{1}{x} \mathbf{1}\{y \leq x\}, \quad [15]$$

94 We compute the unconditional probability density of y ,

$$95 f_Y(y) = \int_0^\infty f_X(x) f_Y(y|X = x) dx = \frac{1}{\theta_{1\text{D}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{y^2}{\theta_{1\text{D}}^2}\right). \quad [16]$$

96 **B. Exact sweep probability.** In one dimension, we obtain a closed-form expression for the exact sweep probability. We start
97 with the sweep probability conditioned on $X = x$ and $Y = y$. The remaining wildtype population is

$$98 N_{\text{wt}} = (2x_{\text{wt}} - 2x_{\text{m}}) \mathbf{1}[0, \tau_1] + (x_{\text{wt}} - x_{\text{m}} + y) \mathbf{1}[\tau_1, \tau_2] \quad [17]$$

99 where $\tau_1 = \frac{x-y}{c_{\text{m}}-c_{\text{wt}}}$ is the time at which the mutant population reaches the first leading edge of the wildtype and $\tau_2 = \frac{x+y}{c_{\text{m}}-c_{\text{wt}}}$
100 is the time at which the mutant reaches the second leading edge of the wildtype such that the sweep is completed. Next, we
101 substitute $x_{\text{wt}} = x + c_{\text{wt}}\tau$ and $x_{\text{m}} = c_{\text{m}}\tau$ and then apply claim 1 to compute the probability that no further mutant arises
102 before the sweep is completed, which leads to

$$103 \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) = e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau} = e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{\alpha_{1\text{D}}^2}} \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha_{1\text{D}} = \sqrt{\frac{c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}}}{\mu}}. \quad [18]$$

104 Then, we marginalize out Y , which gives us

$$105 \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x) = \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) f_Y(y|X = x) dy = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\alpha_{1\text{D}}}{2x} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{1\text{D}}}\right)^2} \text{erf}\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{1\text{D}}}\right), \quad [19]$$

106 where $\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt$ is the Gaussian error function. The exact formula for the unconditional sweep probability is
107 obtained by marginalizing out X . The result is

$$108 \Pr(\text{sweep}) = \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x) f_X(x) dx = \frac{\beta' \cot^{-1}(\sqrt{1 + \beta'})}{\sqrt{1 + \beta'}}, \quad [20]$$

109 which is independent on the mutation rate. Here, $\beta' = \frac{c_{\text{m}}-c_{\text{wt}}}{c_{\text{wt}}}$ is the speed difference relative to the wildtype speed.

110 **C. Approximate sweep probability.** We use the approximation explained in the main text and set $y = 0$, which translates into
 111 probability density $f_Y(y|X = x) = \delta(y)$. Under this assumption, the conditional sweep probability is

$$112 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x) = \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = 0) = e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta_{1D}}\right)^2}. \quad [21]$$

113 and the unconditional sweep probability becomes

$$114 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x) f_X(x) dx = \frac{c_m - c_{wt}}{c_m}. \quad [22]$$

115 Using Bayes theorem, we compute the probability distribution of X given a sweep has occurred,

$$116 \quad f_X(X = x|\text{sweep}) = \frac{2x}{\theta_{1D}^2 \beta} e^{-\frac{x^2}{\theta_{1D}^2 \beta}}, \quad [23]$$

117 where $\beta = \frac{c_m - c_{wt}}{c_m}$. The distribution of X is still described by a Weibull distribution with shape parameter 2. The difference is
 118 only a scaling factor of the characteristic length $\theta_{1D} \rightarrow \theta_{1D} \sqrt{\beta}$.

119 6. Sweep probability in two dimensions

120 We consider a population that is expanding radially in two dimensions at constant speed. If x_{wt} is the radius of the wildtype
 121 population, then the population size is $N = \pi x_{wt}^2 = \pi (c_{wt} t)^2$. We follow the derivations in the main text.

122 **A. Arrival time and location of the first mutant.** We start and compute the probability density for the time at which the first
 123 mutant arises. Using claim 1, we compute the probability that no mutant occurs until time t ,

$$124 \quad P_0 = e^{-\mu \int_0^t \pi c_{wt}^2 t'^2 dt'} = e^{-\mu \frac{\pi}{3} c_{wt}^2 t^3} = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa_{2D}}\right)^3} \quad \text{with} \quad \kappa_{2D} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3}{\mu \pi c_{wt}^2}}. \quad [24]$$

125 Taking the derivative gives us the probability density for the arrival time of the first surviving mutant,

$$126 \quad f_T(t) = \frac{d(1 - P_0)}{dt} = \frac{3t^2}{\kappa_{2D}^3} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa_{2D}}\right)^3}. \quad [25]$$

127 We perform a change of variables $t = \frac{x}{c_{wt}}$ to obtain the probability density for the radius of the wildtype population X at the
 128 time the first mutant arises that is

$$129 \quad f_X(x) = \frac{3x^2}{\theta_{2D}^3} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta_{2D}}\right)^3}, \quad \text{with} \quad \theta_{2D} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3c_{wt}}{\pi \mu}}. \quad [26]$$

130 To compute the probability density for the distance Y between the first mutant and the centre of the wildtype population,
 131 we notice that there at distance y , there are $2\pi y dy$ dividing cells at distance y . Given that the first mutant occurred when
 132 the wildtype population had radius $X = x$, we have $f_Y(y|X = x) \propto y$. After taking care of the boundary condition and
 133 normalization, we obtain

$$134 \quad f_Y(y|X = x) = \frac{2y}{x^2} \mathbf{1}\{y \leq x\}, \quad [27]$$

135 The unconditional probability density of y is

$$136 \quad f_Y(y) = \int_0^\infty f_Y(y|X = x) f_X(x) dx = \frac{2y}{\theta_{2D}^2} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{y^3}{\theta_{2D}^3}\right). \quad [28]$$

137 **B. Exact sweep probability.** We start by finding the expression for the remaining wildtype population N_{wt} given that $X = x$
 138 and $Y = y$. As in the three- and one-dimensional cases, we have the remaining wildtype population given by two formulas such
 139 that

$$140 \quad N_{wt}(\tau) = (\tilde{N}_{wt}(\tau) - \Delta_1(\tau)) \mathbf{1}\{[0, \tau_1]\} + (\tilde{N}_{wt}(\tau) - \Delta_2(\tau)) \mathbf{1}\{[\tau_1, \tau_2]\} \quad [29]$$

141 with $\tau_1 = \frac{x-y}{c_m - c_{wt}}$ and $\tau_2 = \frac{x+y}{c_m - c_{wt}}$. The population sizes of undisturbed growth are given by the area of discs with radii x_{wt}
 142 and x_m

$$143 \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{N}_{wt}(\tau) &= \pi x_{wt}^2 \\ \Delta_1(\tau) &= \pi x_m^2 \end{aligned} \quad [30]$$

144 and the area of wildtype replaced by the mutant after $\tau > \tau_1$ is given by the intersecting area between two discs with radii x_{wt} ,
 145 x_m at distance y taken from ref. (2) which becomes

$$146 \quad \begin{aligned} \Delta_2(\tau) &= x_{wt}^2 \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{y^2 + x_{wt}^2 - x_m^2}{2yx_{wt}}\right) + x_m^2 \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{y^2 + x_m^2 - x_{wt}^2}{2yx_m}\right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}((-y + x_{wt} + x_m)(y + x_{wt} - x_m)(y - x_{wt} + x_m)(y + x_{wt} + x_m))^{1/2}. \end{aligned} \quad [31]$$

147 Again, we replace $x_{\text{wt}} = x + c_{\text{wt}}\tau$ and $x_{\text{m}} = c_{\text{m}}\tau$.

148 Applying claim 1 on the remaining wildtype population, we obtain the conditional sweep probability

$$149 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) = \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y), \quad [32]$$

150 which can be solved numerically. The unconditional sweep probability is then given by the integral

$$151 \quad \begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) f_Y(y|X = x) f_X(x) dy dx, \\ &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau} \frac{2y}{x^2} \frac{3x^2 e^{-x^2/\theta_{2\text{D}}^3}}{\theta_{2\text{D}}^3} dy dx, \end{aligned} \quad [33]$$

152 which we solved numerically.

153 **C. Independence of the mutation rate.** We apply lemma 1 on the integral form of $\Pr(\text{sweep})$ by defining $\nu = \mu$ and

$$154 \quad \begin{aligned} H(x, y) &= \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau + x^3 \frac{3c_{\text{wt}}}{\pi}, \\ P(x, y) &= 2y \times 3x^2, \\ Q(x, y) &= x^2 \frac{\pi}{3c_{\text{wt}}}, \end{aligned} \quad [34]$$

155 which are homogeneous and have degrees $h = 3$, $p = 3$ and $q = 2$. It follows that

$$156 \quad \begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= \mu \times \int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\mu H(x, y)} \frac{P(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} dy dx \\ &\propto \mu \times \mu^{\frac{2-3-2}{3}} = \mu^0, \end{aligned} \quad [35]$$

157 which proves independence of the mutation rate.

158 **D. Approximate sweep probability.** We use the approximation explained in the main text and set $y = 0$, which translates into a probability density $f_Y(y|X = x) = \delta(y)$. Under this assumption, the conditional sweep probability is given by

$$160 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x) = \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = 0) = e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{2\text{D}}}\right)^3}, \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha_{2\text{D}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3(c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}})^2}{\pi\mu(2c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}})}} \quad [36]$$

161 and the unconditional sweep probability becomes

$$162 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = \left(\frac{c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}}}{c_{\text{m}}}\right)^2 \quad [37]$$

163 Using Bayes theorem, we compute the probability distribution of X given a sweep has occurred,

$$164 \quad f_X(X = x|\text{sweep}) = \frac{3x^2}{\theta_{2\text{D}}^3 \beta^2} e^{-\frac{x^3}{\theta_{2\text{D}}^3 \beta^2}} \quad [38]$$

165 where $\beta = \frac{c_{\text{m}} - c_{\text{wt}}}{c_{\text{m}}}$. The distribution of X is still described by a Weibull distribution with shape parameter 3. The difference is
166 only a scaling factor of the characteristic length $\theta_{2\text{D}} \rightarrow \theta_{2\text{D}}\beta^{\frac{2}{3}}$.

167 7. Sweep probabilities in other growth models

168 We focused on constant radial expansion speeds in spatial populations for reasons explained in the main text. However, to
169 obtain more generality, we also computed sweep probabilities in other growth models.

170 **A. Constant population with radially expanding mutant.** We consider a constant population of spherical form with radius x_0
171 leading to total population size $N_0 = \frac{4}{3}\pi x_0^3$. The probability distribution of the wildtype radius X at the time the first mutant
172 arises is fixed at x_0 and is formally written as delta function,

$$173 \quad f_X(x) = \delta(x - x_0). \quad [39]$$

174 The probability density for the distance Y between the first mutant and the centre of the wildtype population conditioned
175 on $X = x$ is the same as for expanding populations. However, we can replace the random variable $X = x$ by the fixed radius
176 x_0 such that

$$177 \quad f(y) = f(y|X = x_0) = \frac{3y^2}{x_0^3} \mathbf{1}\{y < x_0\}. \quad [40]$$

178 Next, we calculate the sweep probability conditioned on X and Y . We denote the remaining wildtype population once
 179 a mutant arose by $N_{\text{wt}}(\tau)$ and analogously to the previous calculation introduce the time measure τ that starts with the
 180 emergence of the first mutant. We have

$$181 \quad N_{\text{wt}} = (\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_1(\tau))\mathbf{1}\{[0, \tau_1]\} + (\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_2(\tau))\mathbf{1}\{[\tau_1, \tau_2]\} \quad [41]$$

182 where the terms are identical to those described in section 3 except for constant wildtype radius x_0 ,

$$183 \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{N}_{\text{wt}} &= \frac{4}{3}\pi x_0^3 \\ \Delta_1(\tau) &= \frac{4}{3}\pi x_m^3 \\ \Delta_2(\tau) &= \frac{\pi}{12y}(x_0 + x_m + y)^2(y^2 + 2yx_m - 3x_m^2 + 2yx_0 + 6x_0x_m - 3x_0^2), \end{aligned} \quad [42]$$

184 and $x_m = x_m(\tau) = c_m\tau$. Using claim 1, the conditional sweep probability is computed by

$$185 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}|Y = y) = e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau} \quad \text{with} \quad \int_0^\infty N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) d\tau = \frac{\pi(45x_0^4 - 210x_0^2y^2 - 23y^4)}{45c_m}. \quad [43]$$

186 Integrating the conditional sweep probability together with $f_Y(y)$ does not yield a closed-form expression.

187 For analytical insight, let us assume again that the mutant originates in the centre of the wildtype population, $f_Y(y) = \delta(y)$.
 188 We then obtain

$$189 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = \Pr(\text{sweep}|Y = 0) = e^{-\frac{\mu\pi x_0^4}{c_m}}. \quad [44]$$

190 We compared this sweep probability for different x_0 to sweep probabilities in expanding populations (Figure 4).

191 Performing the same analysis in one and two dimensions, we obtain

$$192 \quad \begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= e^{-\frac{\mu x_0^2}{2c_m}} \quad \text{in 1D} \\ \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= e^{-\frac{2\mu\pi x_0^3}{3c_m}} \quad \text{in 2D.} \end{aligned} \quad [45]$$

193 **Comparison with Ralph & Coop:** Motivated by parallel adaptation on the species level, Ralph & Coop investigated selective
 194 sweeps in constant populations using a similar approach (3). However, whereas we assume spherical wildtype populations,
 195 Ralph & Coop consider a general shapes and use scaling arguments. To derive a concrete expression, they ignore boundary
 196 effects and obtain "the expected number of other mutations to arise in an area of diameter a in the time it takes the wave to
 197 cover that area". Simplifying eqn. (4) in ref. (3) and keeping their notation, we have

$$198 \quad \frac{2a^3\lambda}{v} \quad \text{in 1D} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\pi a^3\lambda}{v} \quad \text{in 2D.} \quad [46]$$

199 The number of mutations arising in an area over time is a Poisson process (claim 1). Thus, we can interpret this number as
 200 mean of a Poisson distribution. A selective sweep has occurred if no other mutation arose and thus the sweep probability reads

$$201 \quad \begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= P_0 = e^{-\frac{2a^2\lambda}{v}} \quad \text{in 1D,} \\ \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= P_0 = e^{-\frac{\pi a^3\lambda}{v}} \quad \text{in 2D.} \end{aligned} \quad [47]$$

202 We identify v as the speed of the mutant c_m , λ as the local mutation rate conditioned on survival $\mu = \tilde{\mu}\rho$ and a as the maximal
 203 travelled distance by the first mutant, which is x_0 in the case we set $y = 0$. Finally, we find the solution of Ralph & Coop (eqn.
 204 47) to be identical to our solution (eqn. 45) up to multiplication by a constant that can be explained by differing boundary
 205 conditions. The conclusion in either case is that full selective sweeps are highly unlikely for sufficiently large population radius
 206 x_0 .

207 **Comparison with Martens et al.:** Martens and colleagues investigated the likelihood of clonal interference and its impact on the
 208 speed of evolution in spatially structured constant-size populations (4), and then studied the implications for understanding
 209 cancer initiation (5). Two modes of evolution are considered: (i) acquisition via subsequent selective sweeps and (ii) acquisition
 210 with parallel arising mutations which interfere with each other. To distinguish between these two modes, the authors compare
 211 the timescale for a surviving mutation to occur, t_{mut} , and the timescale for a mutation to sweep through the entire constant
 212 wildtype population, t_{fix} . Equating these two timescales leads to a critical length of the wildtype population:

$$213 \quad \begin{aligned} L_c &= \left(\frac{c_0}{2s_0\mu}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{in 1D} \\ L_c &= \left(\frac{c_0}{2s_0\mu}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad \text{in 2D.} \end{aligned} \quad [48]$$

214 The authors argue that clonal interference is very likely in populations of size $L \gg L_c$, whereas we should expect selective
 215 sweeps when $L \ll L_c$. To compare this result with our model, we put L_c into eqn. 45. Therefore, we match parameters by
 216 $c_0 \leftrightarrow c_m$, $2s\mu \leftrightarrow \rho\tilde{\mu} = \mu$ and $x_0 \leftrightarrow L$ leading to

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pr(sweep)} &= e^{-\frac{x_0^2}{2L_c^2}} \quad \text{in 1D} \\ \text{Pr(sweep)} &= e^{-\frac{\pi x_0^3}{3L_c^3}} \quad \text{in 2D.} \end{aligned} \quad [49]$$

218 Indeed, we have $\text{Pr(sweep)} \rightarrow 0$ for $x_0 \gg L_c$ and $\text{Pr(sweep)} \rightarrow 1$ for $x_0 \ll L_c$. We conclude that the result of Martens et al.
 219 are in agreement with our result for constant population sizes.

220 **B. Exponential growth.** We consider an exponentially growing population, $N(t) = e^{rt}$. Applying claim 1, the probability that
 221 no mutants occur until time t is given by

$$P_0 = e^{-\mu \int_0^t e^{rt'} dt'} = e^{-\frac{\mu}{r}(e^{rt} - 1)}. \quad [50]$$

223 Dropping the -1 , this equation coincides with the solution for the stochastic birth-death process obtained by Durrett (eqn.
 224 [25] in Ref. (6)) up to the constant V_0 that is caused by fluctuations in early growth history and is neglected within our
 225 deterministic growth assumption. We proceed to calculate the probability density of T by

$$f(t) = \frac{d(1 - P_0)}{dt} = \mu e^{rt} e^{-\frac{\mu}{r} e^{rt}}, \quad [51]$$

227 Instead of asking for the radius, it is more sensible to ask for the population size of the wildtype at the arrival of the first
 228 mutant. We write $N_x = e^{rt}$, such that $t = \frac{1}{r} \ln(N_x)$. After substitution, we have

$$f_{N_x}(N_x) = \frac{\mu}{r} e^{-\frac{\mu}{r} N_x}, \quad [52]$$

230 which is an exponential distribution. The probability for the radius X can then be calculated by assuming spherical growth
 231 starting from one cell, $N_x = \frac{4}{3}\pi x + 1$. For mathematical convenience, we neglect the $+1$ term. The probability distribution of
 232 X reads

$$f_X(x) = \frac{3x^2}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3} e^{-\frac{x^3}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3}} \quad \text{with} \quad \theta_{\text{exp}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3r}{4\pi\mu}}. \quad [53]$$

234 Exponential growth does not assume a particular spatial structure and the dispersal mode of the mutant is unclear.
 235 Nevertheless, no such assumptions are required to compute the location at which the first mutant arises. The conditional
 236 probability distribution of Y remains the same as in our main model, that is

$$f_Y(y|X = x) = \frac{3y^2}{x^3} 1\{y \leq x\}. \quad [54]$$

238 To obtain the unconditional probability for y , we can marginalize out X giving us

$$\begin{aligned} f_Y(y) &= \int_0^\infty f_Y(y|X = x) f_X(x) dx \\ &= \frac{9y^2}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3} \int_y^\infty \frac{e^{-\frac{x^3}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3}}}{x} dx \\ &= \frac{3y^2}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3} \text{Ei}\left(\frac{x^3}{\theta_{\text{exp}}^3}\right), \end{aligned} \quad [55]$$

240 where $\text{Ei}(z) = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{t} e^{-t} dt$ is the exponential integral function.

241 In the exponential growth model, there is no competition such that the wildtype population will never go extinct and the
 242 mutant will never become fixed. We can however compute whether the mutant reaches a certain frequency χ before another
 243 mutant arises. We assume deterministic growth of the wildtype and the mutant and random time for the emergence of the
 244 mutant. Denoting the wildtype population size by N_{wt} and mutant population size by N_{m} , we have

$$\chi = \frac{N_{\text{m}}}{N_{\text{m}} + N_{\text{wt}}}. \quad [56]$$

246 Now, define t_1 to be the time at which the first mutant occurs and let t_2 be the time at which the mutant has grown to
 247 frequency χ . Then

$$\chi = \frac{e^{r_{\text{m}} t_2}}{e^{r_{\text{m}} t_2} + e^{r_{\text{wt}}(t_1 + t_2)}}. \quad [57]$$

249 Here, t_1 is a random variable that follows the probability density described by eqn. 51, and t_2 can be computed by solving the
 250 equation for χ giving us

$$251 \quad t_2 = \frac{r_{\text{wt}} t_1 - \ln\left(\frac{1-\chi}{\chi}\right)}{r_{\text{m}} - r_{\text{wt}}}. \quad [58]$$

252 The conditional sweep probability (or more precisely the probability for the first mutant to reach frequency χ without
 253 interference of another mutant) is given by

$$254 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}|T = t_1) = e^{-\lambda} \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda = \mu \int_0^{t_2} e^{r_{\text{wt}}(t_1+\tau)} d\tau = \frac{\mu}{r_{\text{wt}}} e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_1} (e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_2} - 1), \quad [59]$$

255 where $t_2 = t_2(t_1)$ is a function of t_1 described above. Eventually, the unconditional sweep probability is computed by

$$256 \quad \begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|T = t_1) \times f_T(t_1) dt_1 \\ &= \int_0^\infty e^{-\frac{\mu}{r_{\text{wt}}} e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_1} (e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_2(t_1)} - 1)} \times \mu e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_1} e^{-\frac{\mu}{r_{\text{wt}}} e^{r_{\text{wt}} t_1}} dt_1 \end{aligned} \quad [60]$$

257 which we solved numerically and present in Figure 4.

258 **C. Boundary growth with proliferation restricted to the boundary.** Antal and colleagues studied aspects of the evolutionary
 259 dynamics in boundary-driven growth where cell proliferation is restricted to the boundary only (7). More properties of this
 260 system have further been studied extensively (8). Whereas we assume turnover of the entire population, Antal et al. consider
 261 turnover only at the boundary and focus on the three-dimensional case. A full selective sweep is impossible in this model since
 262 individuals located away from the boundary neither proliferate nor die. Instead, we can consider the probability that a mutant
 263 will envelop the wildtype and thus becomes the only proliferating population. Using this interpretation, eqn. (17) in ref. (7)
 264 provides the unconditional sweep probability that is

$$265 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = \frac{9 + \beta^2}{\beta^2} \frac{2}{1 + e^{3\pi/\beta}}, \quad [61]$$

266 with $\beta = \sqrt{v^2 - 1}$ and we can identify $v = \frac{c_{\text{m}}}{c_{\text{wt}}}$. The unconditional sweep probability is independent of the mutation rate just
 267 like in our model. Furthermore, Antal et al. find similar expressions for the arrival time of the first mutant $f_T(t)$ (eqn. 15 in
 268 (7)) and the conditional sweep probability $\Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x)$ (eqn. 16 in ref. (7)) as well as the size of the wildtype population
 269 when the first mutant occurs (eqn. 25 in ref. (7) provides the cumulative density function). The unconditional sweep probability
 270 in the case of boundary-restricted proliferation is lower compared to the sweep probability allowing proliferation throughout
 271 the tumour including the interior (Figure 4).

272 **D. Constant population with logistically growing mutant population.** In a well-mixed constant population, it is reasonable to
 273 assume logistic growth for the mutant. This case was considered by Gerrish and Lenski (9) who used a similar methodology to
 274 ours. If the mutant has selective advantage s over the wildtype, the growth of the mutant starting from a single cell can be
 275 written as

$$276 \quad N_{\text{m}}(t) = \frac{N_0 e^{st}}{N_0 - (1 - e^{st})}. \quad [62]$$

277 Here N_0 is the total population size acting as carrying capacity. The remaining wildtype population is $N_{\text{wt}}(t) = N_0 - N_{\text{m}}(t)$.
 278 If μ is the mutation rate for beneficial mutations that survive drift, then there are $\mu N_{\text{wt}}(t) dt$ mutants generated at time t
 279 and the likelihood that at least one interfering mutant arises follows from the application of claim 1. The probability for a
 280 successful sweep is

$$281 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = e^{-\lambda} \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda = \int_0^{t_{\text{end}}} \mu N_{\text{wt}}(t) dt, \quad [63]$$

282 where t_{end} defines the time at which the sweep has completed have there been no interfering mutants. In logistic growth, the
 283 carrying capacity is only approached asymptotically, thus we define t_{end} as the time when all cells except 1 is replaced, that is

$$284 \quad N_{\text{m}}(t_{\text{end}}) = N_0 - 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad t_{\text{end}} = \frac{2}{s} \ln(N_0 - 1). \quad [64]$$

285 Putting this expression into eqn. 63, we obtain $\lambda = \mu \frac{N_0}{s} \ln(N_0 - 1) \approx \mu \frac{N_0}{s} \ln(N_0)$, and the sweep probability becomes

$$286 \quad \Pr(\text{sweep}) = N_0 e^{-\mu \frac{N_0}{s}}. \quad [65]$$

287 This formula is a simplified version of eqn. 3 in ref.(9). Gerrish and Lenski assumed that the selective advantage of mutants is
 288 exponentially distributed and considered interference only if the interfering mutants had higher fitness than the primary mutant.
 289 We have instead assumed that all mutants have the same fitness, and we absorbed the survival of drift into the mutation rate.

290 **E. Sigmoidal growth.** Because biological systems cannot grow indefinitely, several models have been developed to describe the
 291 dynamics of a population that initially grows exponentially but is bounded by a carrying capacity (10). The most common
 292 sigmoidal growth model is logistic growth. If there are at least two subpopulations with different growth parameters, the
 293 logistic growth model can be naturally extended to a competitive Lotka-Volterra system. Closed-form expressions are typically
 294 not obtained. Furthermore, the competition can be implemented in several ways. A fitness advantage in Lotka-Volterra systems
 295 can be obtained by an increased growth rate, an increased carrying capacity, or frequency-dependent competition factors that
 296 are the subject of evolutionary game theory (e.g. (11)). A study of selective sweeps in sigmoidal growth models thus comes
 297 with further complications that cannot be solved with methods presented in this paper alone.

298 Nevertheless, until the first mutant arises, there is only one population type (and thus no complicated competition between
 299 different types). We can thus compute the time and location of the first surviving mutant. We consider a population that
 300 grows logistically according to $N(t) = \frac{K}{1+Ke^{-rt}}$. We apply claim 1, and obtain the probability no mutation occurs until time t ,

$$301 \quad P_0 = e^{-\frac{\mu K}{r} \ln\left(\frac{e^{rt}+K}{K+1}\right)}. \quad [66]$$

302 The probability density is then obtained by taking the derivative,

$$303 \quad f_T(t) = \frac{d(1-P_0)}{dt} = \frac{\mu K(K+1) \frac{\mu K}{r} e^{rt}}{(e^{rt}+K) \frac{\mu K}{r} + 1}. \quad [67]$$

304 The probability density for the population size N_x at the time the first mutant arises can be obtained by substituting
 305 $N_x = \frac{K}{1+Ke^{-rt}}$ yielding

$$306 \quad f_{N_x}(N_x) = \frac{\mu(K+1) \frac{\mu K}{r} (K-N_x) \frac{\mu K}{r} - 1}{rK \frac{2\mu K}{r} - 1}. \quad [68]$$

307 Assuming spherical growth, $N_x = \frac{4}{3}\pi x^3$, the probability density for the radius X can be obtained by substituting $N_x = \frac{4}{3}\pi x^3$.
 308 We obtain

$$309 \quad f_X(x) = \frac{\mu(K+1) \frac{\mu K}{r} \left(K - \frac{4\pi x^3}{3}\right) \frac{\mu K}{r} - 1}{rK \frac{2\mu K}{r} - 1} 4\pi x^2. \quad [69]$$

310 The distance Y of the first mutant from the wildtype's origin conditioned on the radius $X = x$ remains the same as before,

$$311 \quad f_Y(y|X=x) = \frac{3y^2}{x^3} 1\{y \leq x\}. \quad [70]$$

312 To obtain the unconditional density for Y , we can marginalize out X ,

$$313 \quad f_Y(y) = \int_0^\infty f_Y(y|X=x) f_X(x) dx. \quad [71]$$

314 which gives us

$$315 \quad \frac{12\pi y^2 \mu(K+1) \frac{\mu K}{r}}{rK \frac{2\mu K}{r} - 1} \int_y^\infty \frac{\left(K - \frac{4\pi x^3}{3}\right) \frac{\mu K}{r} - 1}{x} dx. \quad [72]$$

316 The integral can be evaluated numerically.

317 **F. Sweep probability at 50%.** To compare the models in the space of parameters (μ, c_m) , we can compute the tuples (μ, c_m) at
 318 which the sweep probability is 50%. The tuples can be expressed as curve $c_m(\mu)$ for which $\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) = 0.5$ leading to the
 319 following expressions for the three-dimensional expansions:

- 320 • Growth throughout (eqn. 14 in the main text): $c_m(\mu) \approx 6.3 c_{\text{wt}}$
- 321 • Boundary proliferation (eqn. 61): $c_m(\mu) \approx 7.2 c_{\text{wt}}$
- 322 • constant population (eqn. 44): $c_m(\mu) = \frac{\mu \pi x_0^4}{\ln(2)}$.

323 We solved the first two expressions numerically.

324 **8. Dependence of the sweep probability on the mutation rate**

325 As explained previously, the mutation rate in an expanding population has two opposing effects on the sweep probability:

326 1. Higher mutation rate \rightarrow earlier arrival of the first surviving mutant \rightarrow smaller wildtype population for the mutant to
327 sweep through \rightarrow higher sweep probability.

328 2. Higher mutation rate \rightarrow earlier arrival of the second, interfering mutant \rightarrow lower sweep probability.

329 In models with fixed population size, effect 1 does not apply, so effect 2 causes the sweep probability to decrease with
330 increasing mutation rate. More precisely, we find $\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) \propto e^{-\mu}$ in the spatial and non-spatial cases.

331 In expanding populations, both effects apply. In the spatial models with constant radial expansion speed, we find that
332 sweep probability is independent of mutation rate, implying that the two opposing effects cancel out. For exponential growth,
333 the sweep probability (or more accurately the probability for the mutant becoming dominant before an interfering mutant
334 arises) increases with mutation rate, implying that effect 1 outweighs effect 2. More precisely, in the exponential case we
335 find $\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) \propto \mu e^{-\mu}$, which is increasing for $\mu \in (0, 1)$. This makes intuitive sense because arising early is of the greatest
336 advantage when the population growth rate increases rapidly over time.

Fig. S1. Simulation results of selective sweep frequencies with different cutoffs in 2D. A selective sweep might be incomplete because of other minority populations. Here, we show simulation results using a weakened definition of a selective sweep. A selective sweep is said to be successful if the mutant's frequency reaches $1 - \epsilon$. The case $\epsilon = 0.00$ corresponds to a complete selective sweep as shown and discussed in the main text. Parameters were set to $m = 0.05$, $K = 16$, $\bar{\mu} = 10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$, $r_{re} = 0.91$, $r_{wt} = 1.0$. We vary over r_m between 1.1 and 3.0 corresponding to different a_m . Conversion between simulation and macroscopic model parameters is described in the Materials and Methods.

Fig. S2. Comparison of simulation results with our analytic predictions of $f_X(x)$ in 2D for different parameter combinations. We use $m = 0.05$, $K = 16$, $r_{re} = 0.91$, $r_{wt} = 1.00$. We vary over the mutation rate μ and r_m corresponding to different a_m . Conversion between simulation and macroscopic model parameters is described in the Materials and Methods.

Fig. S3. Comparison of simulation results with our analytic predictions of f_Y in 2D for different parameter combinations. We use $m = 0.05$, $K = 16$, $r_{re} = 0.91$, $r_{wt} = 1.00$. We vary over μ and r_m corresponding to different a_m . Conversion between simulation and macroscopic model parameters is described in the Materials and Methods.

Fig. S4. Comparison of simulation results with our analytic predictions of $f_X(x|\text{sweep})$ in 2D. We use $m = 0.05$, $K = 16$, $r_e = 0.91$, $r_{wt} = 1.00$, $r_m = 1.3$ and $\tilde{\mu} = 10^{-5}$ leading to speeds $c_{wt} = 0.15$ and $c_m = 0.31$ and survival probability $\rho = 0.23$ (see Materials and Methods).

	1D	2D	3D
$f_X(x)$	$\frac{2x}{\theta_{1D}^2} e^{-\frac{x^2}{\theta_{1D}^2}}$	$\frac{3x^2}{\theta_{2D}^3} e^{-\frac{x^3}{\theta_{2D}^3}}$	$\frac{4x^3}{\theta^4} e^{-\frac{x^4}{\theta^4}}$
$f_Y(y X=x)$	$\frac{1}{x} \mathbf{1}\{y \leq x\}$	$\frac{2y}{x^2} \mathbf{1}\{y \leq x\}$	$\frac{3y^2}{x^3} \mathbf{1}\{y \leq x\}$
$f_Y(y)$	$\frac{1}{\theta_{1D}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{y^2}{\theta_{1D}^2}\right)$	$\frac{2y}{\theta_{2D}^2} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{y^3}{\theta_{2D}^3}\right)$	$\frac{3y^2}{\theta^3} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{y^4}{\theta^4}\right)$
$\Pr(\text{sweep} X=x, Y=y)$	$e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{\alpha_{1D}}}$	numerical evaluation	$e^{-\mu(Ax^4+By^4+Cx^2y^2)}$
$\Pr(\text{sweep} X=x)$	$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}\alpha_{1D}}{2x} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{1D}}\right)^2} \text{erf}\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{1D}}\right)$	numerical evaluation	numerical evaluation
$\Pr(\text{sweep} X=x, Y=0)$	$e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{1D}}\right)^2}$	$e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_{2D}}\right)^3}$	$e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^4}$
$\Pr(\text{sweep})$ [approx.]	$\frac{c_m - c_{\text{wt}}}{c_m}$	$\left(\frac{c_m - c_{\text{wt}}}{c_m}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{c_m - c_{\text{wt}}}{c_m}\right)^3$
$\Pr(\text{sweep})$ [exact]	$\frac{\beta'}{\sqrt{1+\beta'}} \cot^{-1}\left(\sqrt{1+\beta'}\right)$	numerical evaluation	numerical evaluation
$f_X(X=x \text{sweep})$ [approx.]	$\frac{2x}{\theta_{1D}^2 \beta} e^{-\frac{x^2}{\theta_{1D}^2 \beta}}$	$\frac{3x^2}{\theta_{2D}^3 \beta^2} e^{-\frac{x^3}{\theta_{2D}^3 \beta^2}}$	$\frac{4x^3}{\theta^4 \beta^3} e^{-\frac{x^4}{\theta^4 \beta^3}}$
$f_X(X=x \text{sweep})$ [exact]	$\frac{\Pr(\text{sweep} X=x) f_X(x)}{\Pr(\text{sweep})}$	numerical evaluation	numerical evaluation

Table S1. Summary of analytical results of our main model for 1D, 2D and 3D.

Model	Sweep probability	Reference
boundary growth and cell proliferation throughout the population	$\int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{wt}(\tau) d\tau} \frac{3y^2}{x^3} \frac{4x^3 e^{-x^4/\theta^4}}{\theta^4} dy dx$ $\leq \left(\frac{c_m - c_{wt}}{c_m} \right)^3$	here
boundary growth and cell proliferation restricted to the boundary	$\frac{8 + \frac{c_m}{c_{wt}}}{\frac{c_m}{c_{wt}} - 1} \frac{2}{1 + \exp\left(3\pi / \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{wt}} - 1\right)\right)}$	Ref. (7)
constant population with radially growing mutant	$e^{-\frac{\mu \pi x^4}{4c_m}}$	Ref. (3, 4) and here
exponential growth	$\int_0^\infty e^{-\frac{\mu}{r_{wt}} e^{rt_1} (e^{r_{wt}t_2(t_1)} - 1)}$ $\times \mu e^{rt_1} e^{-\frac{\mu}{r} e^{rt_1}} dt_1$	here
constant population with logistically growing mutant	$N_0 e^{-\mu \frac{N_0}{s}}$	Ref. (9) and here

Table S2. Summary of sweep probabilities for different growth models in 3D.

337 **References**

- 338 1. EW Weisstein, Sphere-sphere intersection. from mathworld—a wolfram web resource. (<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/Sphere-SphereIntersection.html>) (2007) Accessed: 22/11/2023.
- 339
- 340 2. EW Weisstein, Circle-circle intersection. from mathworld—a wolfram web resource. (<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/Circle-CircleIntersection.html>) (2003) Accessed: 22/11/2023.
- 341
- 342 3. P Ralph, G Coop, Parallel adaptation: one or many waves of advance of an advantageous allele? *Genetics* **186**, 647–668
- 343 (2010).
- 344 4. EA Martens, O Hallatschek, Interfering waves of adaptation promote spatial mixing. *Genetics* **189**, 1045–1060 (2011).
- 345 5. EA Martens, R Kostadinov, CC Maley, O Hallatschek, Spatial structure increases the waiting time for cancer. *New journal*
- 346 *physics* **13**, 115014 (2011).
- 347 6. R Durrett, *Branching process models of cancer*, Mathematical Biosciences Institute Lecture Series. (Springer), (2015).
- 348 7. T Antal, P Krapivsky, M Nowak, Spatial evolution of tumors with successive driver mutations. *Phys. Rev. E* **92**, 022705
- 349 (2015).
- 350 8. KS Korolev, et al., Selective sweeps in growing microbial colonies. *Phys. biology* **9**, 026008 (2012).
- 351 9. PJ Gerrish, RE Lenski, The fate of competing beneficial mutations in an asexual population. *Genetica* **102**, 127–144
- 352 (1998).
- 353 10. S Benzekry, et al., Classical mathematical models for description and prediction of experimental tumor growth. *PLoS*
- 354 *computational biology* **10**, e1003800 (2014).
- 355 11. W Huang, C Hauert, A Traulsen, Stochastic game dynamics under demographic fluctuations. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **112**,
- 356 9064–9069 (2015).